

Optical Wireless Access with Phased- / Focal-Plane Array Beamformers and Multi-Core Coupled APD Diversity Receiver

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Abstract We present a straight-lane OWC link with beamformers at mobile user and hotspot. We offset free-space path loss through diversity gain realized by a mode-coupling receiver, enabling reception at 1-Gb/s at a BER of 10^{-10} for an OWC budget of 55.2 dB – without optical amplifier. ©2025 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

The future bandwidth, data processing and transmission demand of 6G access renders optical wireless communications (OWC) as EMI-robust, spectrally rich and license-free solution [1]. High communication bandwidths can be yielded, especially when introducing pencil-beam schemes. However, this advancement calls for efficient and precise beam control, which due to complexity often hinders a practical deployment. Micro-mirrors and optical beamformers have been investigated as an attractive solution that offers beam steering [2-5], beam relay in non-line-of-sight scenarios [6] and mitigation of signal fading due to optical turbulence [7, 8].

In this work, we demonstrate a 1-Gb/s OWC link that builds on a glass-based optical phased array (OPA) beamformer at a mobile unit, enabling beam steering on the way to its access hotspot, where robust fiber coupling is facilitated through a focal plane array (FPA) beamformer. We offset the increased OWC path loss due to fan-shaped beam emission through a diversity configuration at the FPA, enabling a BER of 10^{-10} at 50 m reach (or an OWC path loss of 50 dB), using a single avalanche photoreceiver.

2. Beamforming-Assisted OWC Access Link

OWC with 1D-steered beams can be beneficial for mobile vehicular units (MU) moving along pre-defined lanes or industrial Internet scenarios. Towards that, the proposed OWC link employs a beamformer combination of simple 1D-OPA and a multi-functional FPA (Fig. 1) to steer the beam emission at the MU and to enable alignment-tolerant fiber coupling at the optical hotspot (OHS), respectively. The OPA is realized through a beamforming network on a glass-based planar lightwave circuit (PLC). It is laid out similarly to an AWG [9] and uses a constant path difference along 101 delay lines, leading to a phase ramp upon wavelength sweep. Therefore, the spatial position at its output plane can be straight-

Fig. 1: MU to OHS coupling through OPA-FPA beamforming.

forwardly translated to the optical frequency of its input. The inset in Fig. 1 shows its emission for visible light, indicating also a spatial free spectral range ζ due to different diffraction orders. In combination with a cylindrical lens in front of the end-fire waveguides, a moderately fan-shaped beam is then emitted. The OPA is arranged so that the elevation angle of the emitted beam can be steered along the z -direction. It supports an illuminated field-of-view (FoV) of 15.4° at a temporal free spectral range of 35 nm, resulting in a tuning angle of $0.50^\circ/\text{nm}$.

At the OHS the end-facet of a photonic lantern with $C = 61$ hexagonally arranged single-mode cores (pitch Π of $36.9 \mu\text{m}$, see inset in Fig. 2a) resembles the focal plane of a FPA beamformer. Alignment-tolerant coupling to a single-mode fiber (SMF) is accomplished by introducing wavelength-agnostic $M \times 1$ space-switching as a beamforming network with $M \geq C$ [10]. Herein, we advance the switched beamforming network to an $M \times N$ interposer configuration: Since the fan-shaped beam is not ideally coupled to a single antenna element of the FPA, multiple cores of the photonic lantern will be illuminated. A diversity gain can thus be offered by bonding the signals of N of these optical antenna elements. For this purpose, a multi-core fiber (MCF) with $N = 7$ uncoupled single-mode cores pitched by $\pi = 35 \mu\text{m}$ facilitates the efficient optical relay of multiple antenna elements to an avalanche photodetector (APD), similar to a mode-coupling receiver. In contrary to diversity schemes where multiple receivers are employed [11] or beam combining is facilitated at the electrical domain [12], only a single receiver is required.

3. Experimental Straight-Lane OWC Link

Figure 2a presents the experimental setup. A tunable EML feeds the PLC-based OPA beamformer,

Fig. 2: (a) OPA-to-FPA OWC link with MCF-assisted receiver. (b) In-door corridor setup. (c) OHS LoS and MU steering angles.

which features an insertion loss (IL) of 1.5 dB. The emission wavelength at the MU can be tuned from 1540.6 to 1550.12 nm through biasing the DFB section of the tunable EML and its output is intensity modulated at 1 Gb/s. The beam that is launched with 4.5 dBm from the OPA is collimated in y -direction by the cylindrical lens, while the divergence in z -direction is unchanged to retain the full FoV of the OPA. After transmission over a free-space channel with a reach L (Fig. 2a) on either lab-scale (2.5 m) or a 52-m long corridor, the signal is received by the FPA beamformer (Fig. 2b). The latter includes a 2" lens with a focal length of $f = 60$ mm and the photonic lantern, which has an average IL of 0.4 dB. We employed 64×1 (IL of 1.6 dB) or 8×8 (IL of 0.6 dB) MEMS switches as interposers towards a SMF or the MCF, respectively. The smaller input dimension of $M = 8 < C$ for the 8×8 switch is due to the unavailability of a 64×8 device. We evaluated the OWC transmission performance through BER testing with (i) a conventional SMF-coupled APD+TIA receiver that is supplied by the FPA through a 64×1 switch, and (ii) the proposed diversity receiver where the 8×8 switch connects the seven antenna elements with highest incident optical power to the seven MCF cores, which directly feed the active APD area. For the purpose of control, the EML wavelength is remotely tuned via a wireless channel from the OHS side.

4. Over-the-Air Coupling Efficiency

We first evaluated the coupling efficiency as a function of the transmission distance L . To emulate communication between a mobile MU and a fixed OHS that overlooks the MU's line of movement, the OHS was elevated to face downwards at a relative height of $\Delta h = 0.65$ m. The emission wavelength at the MU and the FPA setting at the OHS were tuned while the MU was moved in the direct line-of-sight (LoS) of the OHS. Figure 3a presents the single-core received optical power (SC ROP, \blacklozenge), the OWC path loss (\blacktriangle) and the optimal pair of feed wavelength at the MU and antenna element at the OHS (\blacksquare). Results are shown for distances from 30 to 50 m.

The lowest OWC path loss of 45.7 dB is reached at 40 m. At this distance, the divergence due to fan-shaping already leads to a 45-cm elongated beam. For distances shorter than 37.5 m the coupling is significantly reduced by >13.1 dB, which is attributed to the steeper LoS angle between MU and OHS, as calculated in Fig. 2c (\blacklozenge). For these elevation angles no suitable OHS antenna elements exist since for the given FPA setup the FoVs of the MU (\blacklozenge) and the OHS (green zone in Fig. 2c) do not overlap any longer. This is evidenced by the OPA-to-FPA coupling matrices, which are presented in Fig. 3b to report the coupled optical power over the wavelength / FPA element plane. There are no bright spots for $L \leq 35$ m, which would indicate a high coupling efficiency. When increasing the distance, the focus of the incident beam moves vertically through the FPA plane. The exact ROP distribution among the FPA antenna elements (Fig. 4a) clearly confirms that the beam is well focused in the horizontal y -dimension due to the cylindrical lens at the MU, while it is diverging vertically (z), leading to an elongated power distribution and the relatively high coupling loss.

In contrast to the expected linear evolution for the optimal wavelength setting (\blacktriangle in Fig. 2c) that would

Fig. 3: (a) ROP, path loss, optimal FPA element and wavelength for various distances. (b) Corresponding OPA-to-FPA coupling.

Fig. 4: ROP distribution over FPA focal plane for (a) 45 m and (b) 2.5 m link. (c) MCF diversity scheme for APD coupling.

compensate for the steadily rising angle upon movement of the MU (\blacklozenge), the actual spectral set-point in Fig. 3a increases at first ($L < 37.5$ m), before it starts to decrease ($37.5 \leq L \leq 42.5$ m) to eventually increase ($L > 42.5$ m). This behavior is explained by the uneven basement floor, leading to faint yet noticeable angular fluctuations in combination with focused optical beams. We further made comparison to a MU configuration with a beam-collimated SMF launch and a fixed coupling angle at $L^* \approx 45$ m for an otherwise unchanged OHS setup. While the peak ROP increases by 13.3 dB at L^* , the limited field of illumination of 0.02° reduces the effective range L_{eff} for which coupling drops by -3 dB to 0.35 m or -15.5 dB with respect to the OPA-supported L_{eff} of 12.5 m. This clearly confirms that the OPA-assisted MU significantly increases the overlap in FoVs between MU and OHS. As the FoV of the FPA scales inversely with the focal length of the lens [10], a lens with shorter focal length, together with a larger number of antenna elements is expected to further boost L_{eff} .

5. Mode-Coupling Receiver and Diversity Gain

Figure 5a investigates the BER performance for the lab-scale OWC system. The performance is evaluated by emulating additional OWC path loss through insertion of a variable optical attenuator (VOA). Comparison is made to fiber-based back-to-back (b2b) transmission (Fig. 5b) of the ROSA-packaged and SMF-coupled APD receiver, which achieves a sensitivity of -39.1 dBm at a BER of 10^{-10} (\blacksquare). For the OWC setup, the divergence of the beam emitted by the MU results in an optical coupling to multiple OHS-side FPA elements, as reported in Fig. 4a. We then applied the proposed diversity reception scheme for which multiple power-bearing FPA elements are relayed to a single APD photoreceiver, using the uncoupled cores of a shared MCF launch (Fig. 2a). No beating occurs among the fed signals when the MCF output pigtail is aligned to the active APD area. To compare the BER performance of the MCF-assisted diversity receiver to the earlier b2b reference, we first evaluated the diversity gain over a purely fiber-based link, for which the OWC channel is replaced by an optical 1×8 splitter connected to the fan-in device of the MCF (Fig. 5b). If only the center core is connected to this splitter, the reception sensitivity is -40.5 dBm (\diamond). More importantly, diversity reception involving all seven cores (\blacklozenge) shows a clear sensitivity gain of ~ 6 dB (δ in Fig. 5) – even though the theoretical diversity gain of 8.4 dB cannot be reached, as the distance between the outermost MCF cores slightly exceeds the active diameter of the APD.

We then re-created a similar beam profile as for $L = 45$ m on our lab-scale setup by deliberately offsetting the focus of the FPA lens by $450 \mu\text{m}$, as shown in Fig. 4b. The seven encircled FPA elements with the highest ROP were then coupled through the 8×8 switch to the seven MCF cores, with the peak ROP being relayed to the center core of the MCF (Fig. 4c). Apart from the additional IL of the switch, there is no penalty for the OWC setup (\triangle, \blacklozenge) when compared to the fiber-based diversity receiver setup (\diamond, \blacklozenge). The diversity gain for reception involving all seven cores once again amounts to ~ 6 dB and we achieve a sensitivity of -46.1 dBm. This leaves an OWC budget of 49.7 [55.2] dB given the actual [or an elevated 10 dBm] OPA launch. This translates to a supported reach from $37.5 \leq L \leq 50$ m, as shown in Fig. 3a for the calculated multi-core (MC) ROP (\bullet). The beneficial impact of the diversity gain is also noticeable when comparing the eye openings for the MCF-assisted APD receiver, which are shown for the same VOA setting (Ξ in Fig. 5a) when illuminating all cores of the MCF or solely its center core.

6. Conclusions

We have demonstrated an OWC link with one-dimensional OPA-to-FPA beamforming. Despite the high OWC path loss of 50 dB at 50 m as a result of fan-shaped beam emission, we accomplish signal

Fig. 5: (a) BER for MCF- and SMF-coupled APD in lab-scale OWC link. (b) All-fiber setup to provide benchmark reference.

detection at a BER of 10^{-10} by virtue of diversity gain accomplished through a single, MCF-coupled APD receiver – without requiring an optical amplifier. Further reach improvement is expected through an increased FoV for the FPA beamformer at the OHS, while 2D beamsteering at the MU is left for future work.

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